

1 **Low-Cost Active Reflector and a Passive Corner Reflector Network to**
2 **assist landslide using Multi-temporal InSAR Monitoring**

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13 **Abstract:** A C-band Low-cost Active Reflector (AR) has been tested in a real
14 experimental campaign aimed at monitoring through **Multi-temporal InSAR** an
15 area threatened by a landslide that occurred in 2019. To monitor and characterize
16 the movement, a network of eight Passive Corner Reflectors and one Active
17 Reflector were installed along a forested slope. A set of 285 interferograms
18 obtained combining 60 Sentinel-1 SAR images were processed to evaluate the
19 stability of the area. The AR, installed in a stable location close to the landslide,
20 was used to provide a reference point in this low coherence area. Despite the high
21 sensitivity of the phase response of such devices to temperature changes, the device
22 operates with a stability of $\pm 2\text{mm}$ in deformation retrieval, a value acceptable for
23 monitoring purposes, with a moderate range of temperature values.

24 **Keywords:** SAR; interferometry; backscatter; radar reflectors.

25 **Introduction**

26 The use of artificial reflectors to assist the monitoring of landslides, glaciers and more
27 generally instable areas, can be necessary when the coherence of the observed areas is
28 rapidly decreasing with time, and the use of Multi-temporal InSAR is compromised or
29 has strongly reduced reliability due to the lack of Permanent Scatterers (PSs) [1-3]. For
30 this reason, the potential of installation on site of passive corner reflectors (PCRs) as an
31 aiding tool in Radar interferometry has been debated for many years [4]. A PCR is used
32 as an accurate and stable target acting as an artificial PS [5]. Its response must guarantee
33 a high detectability against the surrounding clutter (i.e. a high Signal-to-Clutter Ratio,
34 SCR) and an adequate amplitude and phase stability over the entire temporal monitoring
35 interval. The use of PCRs was first aimed at calibration purposes [6][7], and later used in
36 SAR interferometry applications [8][9]. The mostly used PCR are metal, triangular- or
37 square-shaped, trihedrals with a size of the order of tens of wavelengths [10]. The larger

38 the size of the PCR, the higher its Radar Cross section (RCS), thus the intensity of its
39 response reaching the satellite receiver, and accordingly the expected precision in
40 interferometric phase measurement, being these two parameters strictly related [4].
41 Hence, to achieve a required value of precision in deformation estimation a minimum
42 value of RCS is demanded. Using SAR imagery acquired at C band, e.g. the case of
43 Sentinel-1 and Radarsat missions, the large PCR size necessary to provide the required
44 performance gives rise to some shortcomings: the required bulky size and weight make
45 the installation costly and difficult, and furthermore, due also to its shape, adverse weather
46 conditions, as heavy rainfall, snowfall, or strong winds can affect or even compromise
47 the quality of its response. An alternative to PCR is represented by active reflectors (AR)
48 [11-16], consisting in Radio Frequency (RF) devices designed to receive, amplify, and
49 retransmit the signal with an intensity clearly detectable by the satellite-borne radar.

50 The effectiveness of the use of active reflectors as an alternative to PCR has been
51 debated in the last years thanks to the availability of a few commercial apparatus [17] and
52 research prototypes [18]. The available solutions have not proved to be fully satisfactory
53 for a main issue, that is the instability of their phase response correlated to environmental
54 temperature variation, which can be not negligible especially for wide temperature range.
55 However, this problem can be reduced using a calibration curve obtained estimating a
56 temperature-dependent factor which allows the partial removal of this seasonal variability
57 [19, 20]. Nevertheless, the AR used in this study provided an acceptable performance for
58 the concerned application. More recently, also the combined use of GPS sensors, AR and
59 PCR has been reported [21][22].

60 This letter presents the results of a field test of an AR developed at CTTC, whose
61 main characteristics are detailed in a previous paper [20]. In this letter we do not address
62 AR technical details, but we report the experimental results obtained installing this AR

63 together with a network of PCRs, in a mountainous landslide where a vegetated slope was
64 selected to be monitored through Multi-temporal InSAR based on Sentinel-1 imagery.
65 The InSAR outputs are integrated into the risk prevention actions developed within the
66 POCTEFA – MOMPA project.

67 **Materials and Methods**

68 *Active and Passive Reflectors*

69 The use of passive reflectors is consolidated since many years and, in the case here
70 discussed, standard square metal trihedrals have been installed. The novelty of this
71 experimental campaign is the joint use of the PCRs with an AR. Passive corner reflectors
72 are targets with a simple geometrical shape, designed to provide high radar reflectivity
73 and a stable phase over time. The reflectivity and the phase stability of PCRs increase
74 with the ratio between their size and the signal wavelength [23], which makes them bulky
75 especially for SAR operating at lower frequencies (e.g. Sentinel-1, Radarsat, SMAP).
76 The simplest AR consists of a set of two antennas, one to receive the satellite signal and
77 the second to retransmit it toward the same satellite, connected through a RF circuit
78 designed to amplify the intensity of the radar signal using the energy available from an
79 external electric source (a battery usually powered by a solar panel). This device can be
80 more compact and lighter than a PCR especially at lower frequency bands, such as C and
81 L band. The mounting setup of an AR is smaller and with a lower air resistance with
82 respect to the installation necessary for a PCR. Although some ARs are already available
83 on the market, the use of these sensors has not widely spread due to some issues among
84 which the most difficult to solve is that, over long temporal interval, the phase response
85 is affected by air temperature variations and hence often not sufficiently stable. The cost
86 of commercial AR is not yet fully competitive with that of a PCR. The used AR was

87 designed with the goal of reducing its cost/benefits ratio with respect to a PCR working
88 at C-band. The main goal of the proposed AR design is to provide the required RCS and
89 phase stability over temporal periods which can cover up to some years. The AR used in
90 this study has been developed at CTTC initially as a research prototype, and it has been
91 carefully tested in laboratory and on field [20]. The design and implementation of this
92 device aim at achieving a trade-off among low-cost, low maintenance, easy and rugged
93 hardware, to allow an easy installation of several devices to be feasible from a cost point
94 of view. The performance of the proposed AR is focused on landslides and glaciers
95 monitoring, without aiming at top geodetic performance, at least in this first version of
96 the device. The tested prototype can work only with a single polarization configuration
97 and one orbital geometry (ascending or descending). The device has been tested with
98 Sentinel-1 imagery, but it is designed to work for any C-band Radar operating also with
99 a slightly larger bandwidth, such as Radarsat. In Table 1 the main characteristics of the
100 AR are resumed. The AR is powered by a low-capacity battery internal to the case
101 connected to an external source as a solar panel or other 12 Volts power sources to
102 maintain the battery charged. Fig. 1a shows a picture of the device taken in the test site.
103 The AR has an internal temperature sensor to follow the thermal behaviour of the case
104 and correct the data when the fluctuations of air temperature demand a phase calibration.

105

Table 1. Main AR properties

Operating mode	Ascending or Descending
Polarization	Single: Co- or Cross-pol
Radar Cross Section (RCS)	>40 dBm ²
Antenna gain	17 dB
RF gain	42 dB
Power consumption	< 0.05 A @ 12V
Operating band	5 405± 50 MHz
Dimensions	520x320x70 (mm ³)

114 a)

b)

115 Fig. 1: a) AR unit; b) PCR#8 mounted close to a GPS unit.

116 *The field setup*

117 **The landslide is a rockslide that could have been induced by roadside excavations,**
 118 **but an exhaustive understanding of the event is ongoing. The CRs are installed on**
 119 **the slope above the rockslide detachment crown, to monitor the behaviour after the**
 120 **stabilization works.** Eight PCRs were installed together with the AR in different
 121 locations covering the monitored area, approximately 25000 square meters. The PCRs
 122 are aluminium square-based trihedral reflectors with trimmed faces, with an inner edge
 123 length of 0.65 m and with a calculated maximum RCS of 33.4 dBm² (C band) [10]. A
 124 GPS unit has been installed close to one PCR, as shown in Fig. 1b. Figure 2 shows a map
 125 of the monitored area with indicated the location of the installed reflectors. The markers
 126 are drawn on a picture of the area before the occurrence of the landslides. **The orientation**
 127 **of AR and PCR are: Azimuth 100° (Nord) for both; elevation: 16° for the PCR, to**
 128 **take into account the direction of peak RCS, which makes a grazing angle of**
 129 **approximately 35. degrees with any of the side plates, and 51° for the AR. Both PCR**

130 and AR are processed as standard PSs.

131 Fig. 2: Map of localization of the artificial reflectors; yellow star indicates the AR while
132 the sky-blue ones the PCRs. The background shows the area before the landslide
133 occurrence.

134 *Sentinel-1 Imagery and Multi-temporal InSAR processing*

135 To estimate the deformation of the area under monitoring we downloaded 60 Sentinel-1
136 SLC images, descending pass (relative orbit number: 110), polarization: VV, acquired
137 from December 4, 2020, to November 30, 2021, 285 interferograms with maximum
138 temporal baseline of 30 days were processed at CTTC [24]. The Digital Elevation Model
139 (DEM) generated by the Shuttle Topographic Mission (SRTM) with 30 m resolution was
140 used. The amplitude image - computed by averaging the 60 images - is shown in Fig.3,
141 where few bright isolated pixels are associated to the passive and active reflectors. Their
142 target position was calculated and converted from GPS coordinates; there are some
143 reflectors 1- or 2-pixel shifts. The presence of strong reflectors as AR and PCRs affects
144 the amplitude of different pixels according to the typical *sinc* function shape response [9].
145 The AR signal is, as expected, is higher than those of the PCRs due to the higher RCS;
146 its RCS is approximately 40 dB m^2 while the value expected from the PCR is 33.4 dBm^2 .
147 Processing the data set through the PSIG interferometric tools available at CTTC [24],

148 we can calculate the deformation velocity, along the Line of Sight (LOS), for the
149 Persistent Scatterers. The chain of the applied processing consists of the following steps.
150 First, after the co-registration of the 60 SLC images, a stack of interferograms with a
151 temporal baseline maximum of 30 days was generated. A mask containing the pixels of
152 reflectors and some additional points was used in this processing. From the set of
153 interferograms, the deformation time series was generated mainly in three steps, including
154 differential topographic error estimation, phase unwrapping, and deformation time series
155 generation from unwrapped phases.

156 Fig. 3: Sentinel-1 mean amplitude Image in radar coordinates obtained averaging 60
157 SLC images, relative orbit 110.

158 *Results*

159 Because of the low coherence of the area, due to the presence of dense vegetation, the
160 deformation can be assessed only in some points corresponding to buildings, structures
161 and the artificial targets installed along the slope. A map of the monitoring area is shown
162 in Fig. 4 which shows the value of the deformation velocity estimated from the temporal
163 series. The background shows the area after the **landslide failure**. The pixels are coloured
164 according to their velocities. In the following analysis, each reflector is associated to a
165 single pixel, the one which shows the maximum amplitude associate to its physical
166 location.

168 Fig. 4: deformation velocity in mm/year estimated from temporal series **of the artificial**
 169 **targets**. The legend represents the deformation velocity scale in mm/year: negative
 170 numbers are displacement velocity away from the satellite position. The data cover the
 171 period: from 4 December 2020 to 23 November 2021. Red and blue arrows indicate the
 172 AR and the buildings taken as reference respectively, while yellow line contours the PCRs
 173 positions.

174 *The Active Reflector*

175 The stability of the area where the AR was installed is confirmed by the evidence that the
 176 AR data show a stable response, whereas the PCRs, whose data are discussed in the
 177 following section, show different trends. Focusing on the AR data, Fig. 5 shows the
 178 deformation times series retrieved during the entire observed period. Some data are
 179 missing due to a fault of the power supply occurred from August 28 to November 10,
 180 2021. Observing the temporal behaviour of Fig.5, we can notice a fluctuation within
 181 approximately $\pm 2\text{mm}$ and an offset especially noticeable after the break due to the power
 182 fault. In general, the overall bias can be ascribed to two causes, i.e. the effect of the slow
 183 temporal trend related to the temperature variation experienced by the device, and the

184 restart of the device after the recovering of the powering system, a possible issue of the
185 phase response of the RF circuit.

186

187 Fig. 5: displacements retrieved from the phase data of the AR vs the date of the Sentinel-
188 1 image acquisition. **The linear regression coefficient of the line is also indicated.**

189

190 To analyse the effect of the temperature variations on the stability of the device we plot
191 the displacement as a function of the temperature measured by the sensor internal to the
192 AR case, which ranges from -5°C to 17° . Both the standard deviation and the bias
193 calculated for the entire temporal slot are lower than 1 mm (calculated standard
194 deviation= 1.03 mm, bias=-0.20 mm). The result, shown in Fig. 6, shows a very slow
195 increasing trend with temperature, smaller than that observed during the laboratory test
196 of the AR detailed in [20], where the experienced temperature was on average higher, and
197 covered a larger range (from 14°C to 32°); the fact that the attained stability is better than
198 that obtained in laboratory can be ascribed to this fact. Furthermore, the calibration curve
199 obtained in laboratory refers to temperatures higher than those measured during the field
200 test and for this reason its use could be not strictly rigorous. Hence, we decided not to

201 apply any correction and consider the attained stability fair to the goals of the current
202 monitoring.

203

204 Fig. 6: displacements retrieved from the phase data of the AR vs the internal temperature
205 of the AR case. **The equation of the linear regression line and its regression coefficient**
206 **are also indicated.**

207 *Passive Reflectors*

208 The deformation of the area is monitored analysing the temporal series of the PCR data.
209 To detail the trend of the PCR, we plot their deformation time series in Fig. 7. Different
210 behaviours are present, ranging from slow to significant deformation rates. The time
211 series associated to PCR# 5 maintains stable along the entire temporal slot, in fact the rate
212 is of the same order of magnitude of the uncertainty of the AR: approximately 1.3
213 mm/year. Although the last acquisitions seem to show a slight trend, this maintains within
214 the uncertainty of the entire set, further acquisitions will make clearer this fact. On the
215 other hand, PCR # 8 shows a noticeable linear deformation slightly higher than 40
216 mm/year. In fig. 7, the regression line for the two corresponding sets of data is also
217 indicated to underline the large difference between the two slope factors. The rest of the
218 PCRs show intermediate values.

219

220 Fig. 7: deformation in mm retrieved from the PCRs vs the Sentinel-1 image acquisition
 221 date. The two green and red dashed lines represent the calculated regression line obtained
 222 for PCR #5 and PCR #8 respectively. The rates of the two equations is expressed in
 223 mm/day and correspond to 1.3 mm/year and 41.6 mm/year for PCR#5 and PCR#8,
 224 respectively. The regression line for the two corresponding sets of data is also indicated.
 225 **The deformation estimated through GPS data acquisitions is also indicated with a**
 226 **dashed yellow line.**

227 **The velocity of deformation at PCR#8 can be compared to the data acquired by a**
 228 **GPS station installed very close to this target. The GPS measurements cover only**
 229 **partially the analysed PCR temporal series (i.e. from 2/7/2021 to 14/11/2021) and**
 230 **provide a -3.5 mm displacement over 136 days, a trend a bit slower than that of**
 231 **PCR#8. In Fig. 7 both data set are shown.**

232 ***Discussion***

233 The slow deformation trend detected in the AR data cannot be associated to an actual
 234 deformation, according to the analysis of stability of this device, as commented in the
 235 previous paragraph. **The fact that there's no evident relationship between**
 236 **deformation time series and temperature, can be ascribed to the limited range of**
 237 **temperature variation: the effect is negligible and the low regression correlation**

238 **coefficient (0.1485), point out that a low correlation exists between AR response and**
239 **temperature.** This allows considering the AR a stable reference to evaluate the PCRs
240 behaviour. It is worth noting that in this experiment we use a network of PCRs of
241 moderate size, to facilitate their installation and improve their mechanical robustness
242 which, however, reduces their performance. The non-optimum size of the reflectors, and
243 the SCR of the area, cannot guarantee a condition capable to provide the highest phase
244 accuracy. Finally, the acquisition of a longer set of data could help the interpretation of
245 this behaviour. The use of an AR with a higher RCS and whose mechanical installation
246 is easier and less affected by harsh weather conditions provided a reference more accurate
247 to analyse the PCR response. The analysis of the AR data shows that this target maintains
248 its stability within a millimetric magnitude. This allows to compare the stable area data
249 with the PCRs' response and assess a widespread linear deformation in the area to be
250 monitored.

251 ***Conclusions***

252 In this letter we experimented the joint use of eight PCRs and one AR as a tool to support
253 the DInSAR based deformation monitoring of a low coherence area: a vegetated slope.
254 The combined use allowed to reduce the installation complexity thanks to the reduced
255 size of the PCR and the high handling of the AR. The AR, despite a certain instability
256 due to the thermal variation occurred during the entire time interval, demonstrated
257 adequate to analyse the response of the other, passive, reflectors. Taking profit of the
258 different characteristics of the two kind of artificial reflectors the authors obtained an
259 estimate of the deformation trend in some points distributed over the monitored area. **A**
260 **comparison between the deformation estimated using PCR#8 and the nearby GPS**
261 **sensor seems to confirm the deformation estimated by PCR network.** Although the
262 validation of these remarks demands a more exhaustive set of data, especially a longer

263 temporal interval, to better assess the behaviour of the AR response, the performance of
264 this setup can be considered satisfactory. An upgrading of the first version of the AR used
265 in this study is in progress to improve its phase stability and make possible a simultaneous
266 dual-polarization configuration capability to provide a more exhaustive information on
267 the radar backscattering of the monitored area.

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